

1 **Time perception and patience: Individual differences in interval timing precision predict choice**
2 **impulsivity in European starlings, *Sturnus vulgaris***

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Abstract

22 Impulsivity, the extent to which rewards are devalued as the time until their realization increases, is
23 linked to various negative outcomes in humans, yet understanding of the cognitive mechanisms
24 underlying it is limited. Variation in the imprecision of interval timing is a possible contributor to
25 variation in impulsivity. We use a numerical model to generate predictions concerning the effect of
26 timing imprecision on impulsivity. We distinguish between fixed imprecision (the imprecision that
27 applies even when timing the very shortest time intervals) and proportional imprecision (the rate at
28 which imprecision increases as the interval becomes longer). The model predicts that impulsivity
29 should increase with increasing fixed imprecision, but decrease with increasing proportional
30 imprecision. We present data from a cohort of European starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris*, $n = 28$) in which
31 impulsivity had previously been measured through an intertemporal choice paradigm. We tested
32 interval timing imprecision in the same individuals using a tri-peak temporal reproduction
33 procedure. We found repeatable individual differences in both fixed and proportional imprecision.
34 As predicted, birds with greater proportional imprecision in interval timing made fewer impulsive
35 choices, whilst those with greater fixed imprecision tended to make more. Contradictory
36 observations in the literature regarding the direction of association between timing imprecision and
37 impulsivity might be clarified by distinguishing between fixed and proportional components of
38 imprecision.

39

40 Keywords: interval timing, scalar expectancy theory, impulsivity, delay discounting, starlings, *Sturnus*
41 *vulgaris*

42 Introduction

43 Impulsivity, in the sense we use it here, refers to the extent by which a reward is devalued as the
44 time to its realization increases. Impulsivity varies between individuals. In humans, greater
45 impulsivity has been linked to psychological conditions ranging from behavioural disorders to
46 addiction (Moeller et al. 2001; Verdejo-García et al. 2008; Patros et al. 2016). In non-human animals,
47 impulsivity is influenced both by current energetic state, and long-term developmental history
48 (Bateson et al. 2015; Dunn et al. 2019). However, in neither humans nor non-human animals do we
49 fully understand the cognitive mechanisms that underlie individual differences in impulsivity. These
50 mechanisms are likely to involve the processing of reward magnitude, or the processing of time
51 intervals, or both.

52 The idea that core cognitive processes relating to time might be different in more impulsive
53 individuals has generated a substantial literature in humans (see Wittmann and Paulus 2008),
54 though there is at present no consensus on exactly what feature of time processing drives variation
55 in impulsivity. Several recent rat studies have found correlations between impulsivity and the
56 *imprecision* of timing in particular. Imprecision is the amount of variation (noise) when an individual
57 repeatedly estimates the same time interval. Two correlational studies found that those individuals
58 whose timing was more imprecise were also more impulsive (Marshall et al. 2014; McClure et al.
59 2014). In these studies, impulsivity was measured by repeated choices between smaller-sooner and
60 larger-later rewards, and timing imprecision was measured by either repeated reproduction of a
61 fixed interval (McClure et al. 2014), or a temporal discrimination task (Marshall et al. 2014). In the
62 former case, animals are trained that a response is available after a fixed interval (FI). The
63 imprecision of their timing is estimated by the temporal spread of their responses about the trained
64 interval. In the latter case, animals are trained to discriminate between a short and a long duration
65 stimulus, then tested on a series of stimuli of intermediate durations. The shape of the logistic
66 function mapping their probability of responding 'long' onto the duration of the stimulus provides an
67 estimate of timing precision.

68 A third rat study (Smith et al. 2015), presents three separate experiments where impulsivity and
69 timing imprecision were measured simultaneously, and then both measured again in the same
70 individuals after an intervention phase. The intervention phase, which varied in detail across the
71 three experiments, consisted of prolonged working on a task requiring the animal to make
72 responses at exact points in time, such as a differential reinforcement of low rates of responding
73 schedule. In all cases, not only had timing imprecision decreased relative to baseline when it was
74 measured again after the intervention phase; the rats had become less impulsive too. Thus, these
75 results suggest that timing imprecision and impulsivity are sufficiently closely linked that the same
76 interventions that affect one also affect the other.

77 Whilst these three rat studies suggest empirically that timing imprecision might be related to
78 impulsivity, they have not formally theorized why this relationship should hold. Intuitively, timing
79 imprecision and impulsivity seem like they should be related. There is a non-linear, convex
80 downward function linking the perceived value of a reward to the delay until its realization. An
81 individual with an imprecise perception of, say, an 8s delay will sometimes perceive that delay as 7s,
82 and sometimes as 9s. Because of the convexity of the discount function, the individual will
83 overestimate the perceived value of the reward when it perceives the delay to be 7s by a greater
84 amount than it will underestimate the perceived value when it perceives the delay to be 9s. Thus, its
85 average valuation of the reward will be greater than if its timing were completely precise, even
86 though its average estimate of the delay is 8s. This is an example of Jensen's inequality (Jensen 1906;
87 Denny 2017).

88 This argument has been used to make the prediction that greater timing imprecision should produce
89 less impulsivity (McClure et al. 2014). The study in fact found the opposite pattern. However, we
90 argue that the prediction is not so straightforward. Impulsivity is typically measured using choices
91 between smaller-sooner and larger-later rewards. Imprecision of interval estimation will apply *both*
92 to the estimation of the short delay to the smaller-sooner reward, and the long delay to the larger-
93 later reward. It is not intuitively obvious which of the two perceived values will be more severely
94 affected (or indeed, whether the effects on the two perceived values will exactly cancel one another
95 out). Moreover, saying that one individual's interval timing is less precise than that of another
96 individual could mean two different things (figure 1): (a) the imprecise individual's variance in
97 perceived delay exceeds that of the precise individual by some constant that is independent of the
98 delay duration; or (b) the imprecise individual's variance in perceived delay increases more steeply
99 with increasing delay than is true for the precise individual. If we model timing imprecision as a
100 linear function of the delay to be estimated, then these two forms of imprecision amount to
101 differences in the intercept (α on figure 1) of the imprecision function (i.e. the variance in estimation
102 of even a very short delay), and the slope (β on figure 1) of the imprecision function. We henceforth
103 refer to the intercept of the imprecision function as the fixed imprecision, and the slope of the
104 imprecision function as the proportional imprecision. It remains to be determined which of the fixed
105 and proportional imprecision ought to affect impulsivity, or whether their effects are even in the
106 same direction. We could find no analytical framework in which to make predictions on this
107 question. We therefore developed a numerical model to explore these questions. We then tested
108 the model's predictions using data from a cohort of European starlings.

109 **Numerical model: How should timing imprecision affect impulsivity?**

110 In our model, individuals discount rewards that arrive after a delay t according to the hyperbolic
111 discounting function (Mazur and Biondi 2009):

$$112 \quad v(t) = \frac{1}{(1 + kt)}$$

113 Here, k is a parameter setting the discount rate or degree of impulsivity. Now, assume that when an
114 individual recalls a delay, they will on average be accurate, but there is some variability in their
115 perceived duration. Specifically, for individual i , the perceived duration of an interval of true
116 duration t is normally distributed as:

$$117 \quad p_{i,t} \sim N(t, \alpha_i + \beta_i t)$$

118 Here, α_i is individual i 's fixed imprecision, and β_i is their proportional imprecision. Scalar expectancy
119 theory states that timing imprecision increases with increasing interval duration, with constant ratio
120 between the mean estimate of the duration and its variance (the scalar variance property; Gibbon
121 1977). Strictly, under scalar variance, fixed imprecision should be zero whilst proportional
122 imprecision should be a positive constant. However, scalar variance does not hold exactly: even in
123 the original studies, there was a small but positive intercept of the regression line of imprecision on
124 FI (Gibbon 1991). This has typically been treated as unimportant noise, and individual differences in
125 this fixed component of imprecision have not been separately characterised. However, it is
126 reasonable to assume that both α and β typically have positive values and can vary between
127 individuals.

128 We simulated the scenario where there are two rewards, one that arrives after 3s and one that
129 arrives after 8s. Our outcome measure is the relative value assigned to the sooner reward compared
130 to the later reward (averaged over 100,000 experiences of each delay, and normalized relative to
131 the values assigned by an individual with perfectly precise timing, i.e. $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = 1$). Hence, a
132 higher relative value would equate to greater impulsivity. We explore the effects of varying the
133 individual's values of α and β .

134 Results are shown in figure 2. Panel A uses $k = 0.54$, the average discount rate estimated from a
135 previous study of European starlings (Bateson et al. 2015). Where the proportional imprecision β is
136 small, increasing the fixed imprecision α produces greater impulsivity. This is intuitive: if there is a
137 constant increment in imprecision that applies to the estimation of both rewards, then its over-
138 valuation impact will be greater on the smaller-sooner reward, because the discount function is
139 steepest at this point. Thus, it will produce greater over-valuation of that reward and greater
140 impulsivity. However, for any given α , increasing the proportional imprecision β *reduces* impulsivity.
141 This is because an excess of proportional imprecision will lead to larger error in the estimation of the
142 delay to the larger-later reward in particular, producing a greater over-valuation of that reward, and
143 hence less impulsivity. As β becomes larger, the differences in impulsivity with increasing α
144 disappear. With 100,000 samples at each delay, these results show very little variation from run to
145 run of the simulations.

146 We also repeated the simulations with both a higher ($k = 1$; figure 2B) and a lower ($k = 0.1$; figure 2C)
147 discount rate parameter. For the high discount rate, the differences in impulsivity with increasing α
148 at low values of β were larger, whereas for the low discount rate, the sensitivity of impulsivity to
149 variation in α was abolished, and the sensitivity of impulsivity to variation in β , although remaining in
150 the same direction, was attenuated. This is because, in the limit as $k \rightarrow 0$, the hyperbolic discount
151 function becomes a horizontal straight line, and Jensen's inequality does not apply.

152 The model shows that we cannot make a global prediction concerning the association between
153 timing imprecision and impulsivity. Instead, timing imprecision must be decomposed into the fixed
154 component (the component of imprecision that is independent of the delay), and the proportional
155 component (the rate by which imprecision increases as the delay increases). The fixed component of
156 imprecision should either be positively associated with impulsivity (greater fixed imprecision, more
157 impulsive; as long as the proportional component is relatively small), or that the association should
158 be null (if the proportional component is large). The proportional component of imprecision should
159 be negatively associated with impulsivity (greater proportional imprecision, less impulsive).

160 In the remainder of this paper, we test these predictions using data from a cohort of European
161 starlings. We measured interval timing using a tri-peak procedure (Hinton and Meck 1997; Paule et
162 al. 1999). Because this involves reproduction of three different interval durations, the tri-peak
163 procedure allows us to separately estimate the fixed and proportional imprecision for each
164 individual. We had a prior measurement of impulsivity from the same birds, based on an
165 intertemporal choice task (Dunn et al. 2019). The birds, which were hand-reared, had undergone a
166 manipulation of developmental conditions that affected their impulsivity (see Dunn et al. 2019 for
167 details). Specifically, individuals raised under the combination of limited food supply and high
168 begging effort were significantly less impulsive than other experimental groups. We thus predicted:
169 (1) that birds with greater fixed imprecision in the timing task would if anything make more
170 impulsive choices in the impulsivity task; (2) that birds with greater proportional imprecision in the
171 timing task would make fewer impulsive choices in the impulsivity task; and (3) that the
172 developmental factors that affected impulsivity would also affect timing imprecision.

173

174 **Methods**

175 *Ethics*

176 Our study adhered to the ASAB/ABS Guidelines for the ethical treatment of animals, was approved
177 by Newcastle University Animal Welfare Ethical Review Board committee and was conducted under
178 U.K. Home Office project licence (number PPL70/8089).

179 *Study animals and developmental manipulation*

180 Subjects were 28 European starlings (15 female, 13 male; sexed molecularly; see Nettle et al., 2017)
181 from 8 natal families belonging to a cohort of 32 chicks hatched in the wild in May 2014 in a nest box
182 population on farms in Northumberland, UK. Three of the cohort had died prior to the present
183 experiment and a further bird failed to complete the tri-peak procedure task; impulsivity data had
184 been successfully obtained for 27 of the 28 birds. As nestlings, the birds were subject to a
185 manipulation of developmental adversity described in full elsewhere (Nettle et al. 2017). Briefly, on
186 post-hatching day 5, quartets of siblings were brought to the lab where they were hand reared. On
187 day 6 and continuing until day 15, we simultaneously manipulated amount of food (hereafter
188 Amount: Plenty or Lean) and the begging effort (Effort: Easy or Hard) experienced by the nestlings,
189 in a 2x2 factorial design. Nestlings allocated to the Plenty groups were fed *ad libitum* to satiation at
190 each feeding visit, while the Lean groups received a proportion of the amount consumed by the
191 corresponding Plenty group (approximately 73%, although this was varied from visit to visit in order
192 to replicate growth trajectories of the slowest-growing chicks in wild nests). To manipulate begging
193 effort, nestlings in the Hard groups received twice as many visits as those in the Easy groups, but
194 were fed during only half of those visits while in the other half they were stimulated to beg for 2 min
195 without receiving food. From day 16 onwards, all birds received *ad libitum* food. The manipulation
196 affected growth rates, body weight and skeletal size at the time of fledging (Nettle et al. 2017). Once
197 the fledglings became independent (approx. four weeks post-hatch), they were transferred into
198 mixed-sex, mixed-treatment groups to two indoor aviaries (215 x 340 cm and 220 cm high; ca. 18°C;
199 40% humidity; 15:9 h light:dark cycle) and were fed *ad libitum* on domestic chick crumb (Special
200 Diets Services 'Poultry Starter (HPS)'), supplemented with cat biscuits (Royal Canin Ltd.), dried insect
201 food (Orlux insect pâté), live mealworms and fruit.

202 *Experimental cages*

203 For both the timing and impulsivity experiments, birds were transferred to individual cages that
204 served both as home cages and operant testing chambers. Cages measured 100 x 45 cm and 45 cm
205 high and were fitted with two wooden perches and two water bottles. Each cage contained an
206 operant panel of three illuminable pecking keys and a feeder trough connected to a pellet dispenser
207 delivering 45 mg grain-based rodent pellets (TestDiet, Richmond, IN, USA), as described in Feenders
208 and Bateson (2013). The panels were controlled remotely using the Whisker Experimental Control
209 system (Cardinal and Aitken 2010), and cognitive tasks were programmed in Microsoft Visual Basic
210 5.0 (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA, U.S.A). Temperature and lighting conditions were the
211 same in the experimental room as in the aviary. There were 8 cages in the experimental room, with
212 acoustic and visual contact between them. Due to the number of cages available, the birds were run
213 in sequential groups of 6 to 8 birds.

214 *Timing imprecision: Tri-peak procedure temporal reproduction task*

215 The tri-peak procedure task began when birds were 1308-1658 days old. The birds had, prior to this
216 study, been trained to peck keys for reward (Andrews et al. 2018). Habituation and operant training
217 procedures followed those described by Dunn et al. (2019). To progress on to the tri-peak procedure
218 task, birds had to peck on at least 80% of initial training trials involving one lit key for three
219 consecutive sessions, or at least 50% of trials for five consecutive sessions. Trials took place between
220 0730 and 1230, with *ad libitum* food (10 g dry cat biscuits, 5 g chick crumb, 5 g dried insect food, a
221 slice of fruit and 4 live mealworms) and water baths provided from 1230 until 1630.

222 Birds were trained on three fixed-interval (FI) reinforcement schedule durations (5 s, 15 s and 45 s)
223 associated with three separate pecking keys. Since we were primarily interested in individual
224 differences and hence required all birds to have the same experience, all birds received the same
225 assignment of key positions to intervals, namely: lefthand key to 5 s, central key to 15 s and
226 righthand key to 45 s. At the start of each trial, the central pecking key was illuminated with amber

227 light. This remained illuminated until the bird initiated a trial by a single peck to this key, whereby
228 the amber light extinguished and all three pecking keys were illuminated in green. On SHORT trials, a
229 single peck to the lefthand key after an interval of 5 s or greater caused all keys to extinguish and
230 initiated the illumination of the hopper light and delivery of one reward pellet. On MEDIUM trials, a
231 single peck to the central key after an interval of 15 s or greater was rewarded with a pellet. On
232 LONG trials, a peck to the righthand key after an interval of 45 s or greater was rewarded with a
233 pellet. There were no consequences of responses on incorrect keys, or early responses on the
234 correct key. An inter-trial interval (ITI) of 100 s began following pellet delivery. Each daily session
235 comprised 2 blocks (beginning 07:30 and 10:10), each with a maximum of 30 trials and ending after
236 2.5 h if a bird had not completed. Within each block, an equal number of SHORT, MEDIUM and
237 LONG trials were presented in random order.

238 Once a bird completed at least 80% of trials each day for 5 consecutive days, SHORT, MEDIUM and
239 LONG trials were randomly interspersed with PROBE trials. In PROBE trials, all keys remained
240 illuminated for 135 s and then extinguished, with no consequences for pecks on any key, and no
241 reward given. The number of trials in each block was increased to a maximum of 40 in this phase,
242 with SHORT, MEDIUM, LONG and PROBE trials presented in equal number in random order. We
243 recorded the number of peck responses on all keys throughout all trials in 0.5 s time bins from the
244 initiation of each trial. Birds were tested seven days a week and completed between 873-2026 trials
245 in total, the procedure ending when all birds in each group had completed at least 9 days with
246 PROBE trials (range 9 –22 days). This large number of trials provided birds with opportunity to learn
247 the FI durations and develop stable responses. We analysed only data from PROBE trials on the final
248 4 days of the task (i.e. a maximum of 40 PROBE trials per bird).

249 *Impulsivity task*

250

251 Data on impulsive choice have been reported fully elsewhere (Dunn et al. 2019). Impulsive choice
252 testing began when birds were aged 978–1044 days. Briefly, birds made repeated simultaneous
253 choices between a smaller-sooner and a larger-later food reward, using the same operant apparatus
254 as above. At the start of each trial, the central pecking key was illuminated with amber light, and a
255 single peck to this key was required to initiate the trial, whereby the amber light extinguished and
256 either a forced or choice trial began. In a forced short-delay trial, pecking a side key illuminated in
257 red produced one 45 mg pellet after a 3 s delay. In a forced long-delay trial, pecking a side key
258 illuminated in green produced two pellets after an 8 s delay. Choice trials were identical to forced
259 trials with the exception that following the initiation peck, both side keys were illuminated (one in
260 red and one in green). A single peck indicated the bird's choice. Birds completed 120 trials (or a
261 maximum of 4 h) per day, 7 days a week and all completed 10 days of the impulsivity task. We used
262 the proportion of completed choice trials on which the bird chose the smaller-sooner key as the
263 measure of impulsivity using data for each bird from day 5 to day 10 of the task inclusive.

264 *Statistical analysis*

265 The raw data and R script are archived in the Zenodo repository (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3971670).
266 Statistical analyses were conducted in R v3.5.1 ("R Development Core Team" 2011) using the base
267 statistical procedures and 'lme4' packages (Bates et al. 2015).

268 Under FI schedules, animals tend to begin responding at a low rate and increase response frequency
269 as the criterion FI approaches. In PROBE trials, where no reward is delivered, response frequencies
270 taper off once the FI has passed. Thus we described birds' timing functions for each of the three FIs
271 using three parameters (Hinton and Meck 1997): (1) Peak Rate – the maximal rate of pecking on the
272 target key, a measure of motivation; (2) Peak time (hereafter Peak) - the time of the maximal rate of
273 pecking, a measure of the bird's central estimate of the FI; and (3) Spread – which we here define as

274 the duration between the lower bound and upper bound time at which the peck rate was half the
275 Peak Rate. This is a measure of timing imprecision, with a larger Spread indicating greater
276 imprecision (Church et al. 1994).

277 To estimate these three parameters, for each bird, we calculated the mean number of responses on
278 each key within each 0.5-s time bin across all PROBE trials during the final 4 days of the task. Next,
279 we fitted 10th-order polynomials to these data for each bird. Tenth order polynomials were chosen
280 following initial exploratory analysis on a subset of data (14 birds, 4 natal families). From the fitted
281 polynomials, we defined the Peak as the time of the maximum fitted value. Peak Rate was defined
282 as the rate of pecking corresponding to the Peak. We then defined as the lower and upper bounds
283 the time at which peck rate equaled half the Peak Rate, and calculated the Spread as defined above.
284 Having obtained, for each bird, a Spread value for each of the FIs, we fitted a linear model with the
285 FI duration as the predictor variable and the Spread as the outcome. The intercept from this model
286 was our estimate of that bird's fixed imprecision, and the slope was our estimate of the bird's
287 proportional imprecision.

288 For the main analyses, we used general linear mixed models incorporating random intercepts for
289 natal family, and individual bird where we had repeated measures. The fixed effects included in each
290 model are described in the relevant Results section and in Table 1. We included sex as a control
291 variable in all analyses of timing performance measures to allow for the detection of sex-specific
292 effects, because sex differences in interval timing occur in rats (McClure et al. 2014); results without
293 controlling for sex are extremely similar. For models including the developmental treatments, we
294 initially included interaction terms (e.g. Amount*Effort) and sequentially removed non-significant
295 interactions to produce the final models reported in Table 1. Measures of Peak and Spread were,
296 where appropriate, normalised across FI durations prior to analysis. Fixed and proportional
297 imprecision were standardized for analysis. Maximum-likelihood estimation was employed
298 throughout. Significance testing for mixed models used Satterthwaite's method in R package
299 'lmerTest'. We assumed a criterion for significance of $p < 0.05$.

300 To examine individual consistency in timing performance measures, we separately fitted
301 polynomials on data from PROBE trials on the final two days of the tri-peak procedure and the two
302 days prior to this, and conducted a variance components analysis to ascertain the proportion of
303 variance explained by individual identity and natal family in fixed and proportional imprecision.

304

305 **Results**

306

307 *Overall timing performance*

308 Key pecking responses on each key were distributed across time with a single peak, as expected
309 (figure 3). On average, birds showed accurate timing, with mean Peak values falling close to the
310 trained FIs (mean \pm SE, SHORT (5 s FI) 4.77 ± 0.18 s; MEDIUM (15 s FI) 14.21 ± 0.60 s; LONG (45 s FI)
311 41.38 ± 1.72 s; figure 3). As expected, average Spread increased with FI for all birds (mean \pm SE,
312 SHORT (5 s FI) 10.27 ± 0.36 s; MEDIUM (15 s FI) 25.34 ± 1.58 s; LONG (45 s FI) 66.45 ± 4.82 s; see
313 figure 4 for data from each bird). However, the birds' performance did not show the scalar variance
314 property. The scalar variance property implies a constant coefficient of variation across FIs (i.e. the
315 Spread divided by the FI should be constant across SHORT, MEDIUM and LONG keys). In fact
316 Spread/FI was significantly higher for SHORT (mean \pm SE 2.05 ± 0.07) than MEDIUM (mean \pm SE 1.69
317 ± 0.11) or LONG (mean \pm SE 1.48 ± 0.11 ; linear mixed model: $\beta_{\text{MEDIUM}} = -0.22$, SE 0.06, $t = -3.65$, $P <$
318 0.001 ; $\beta_{\text{LONG}} = -0.38$, SE 0.06, $t = -6.43$, $P < 0.001$; figure S1). This implies the existence of fixed as well
319 as proportional imprecision in the birds' timing performance. Indeed, birds displayed non-zero fixed
320 imprecision overall (mean \pm SE: 3.76 ± 1.18 s, t-test against $\mu = 0$, $t = 3.19$, $P = 0.004$) as well as non-

321 zero proportional imprecision overall (mean \pm SE: 1.40 ± 0.12 s, t-test against $\mu = 0$, $t = 11.28$, $P <$
322 0.001). Birds with greater fixed imprecision showed lower proportional imprecision ($r = -0.79$, $P <$
323 0.001).

324 *Timing imprecision and impulsivity*

325 To examine the relationship between choice impulsivity and interval timing precision, we ran two
326 models with proportion of choices for the smaller-sooner reward as the outcome variable, and fixed
327 or proportional imprecision as the predictor variables (table 1, models 1 and 2). The high degree of
328 collinearity between fixed and proportional imprecision prevented them being entered
329 simultaneously into the same model (see Discussion). The association between fixed imprecision and
330 impulsivity was non-significantly positive (table 1, model 1; figure 5A). Proportional imprecision
331 significantly predicted choice impulsivity, negatively, with more imprecise birds making fewer
332 choices for the smaller-sooner reward (table 1, model 2; figure 5B).

333 *Effects of developmental experience, individual identity, natal family and sex on timing performance*

334 We modelled birds' fixed imprecision and proportional imprecision as outcome variables, with the
335 developmental treatments Amount and Effort, as well as their interaction, as fixed predictors (table
336 1 models 3 and 4). Developmental treatments did not significantly predict either fixed imprecision
337 (figure 6A) or proportional imprecision (figure 6B). However, it is noteworthy that the experimental
338 group that were significantly less impulsive than the others (Lean-Hard) also had the highest average
339 proportional imprecision values (figure 6B).

340 We also carried out exploratory analyses of whether developmental treatments predicted birds'
341 Peak, Peak Rate or Spread for each key (table 1 models 5-7). Amount significantly predicted Spread
342 (table 1, model 5). Across keys, birds raised on a Lean diet had larger Spreads than those raised with
343 Plenty to eat as nestlings (estimated marginal means \pm SE: Lean 0.28 ± 0.20 , Plenty -0.27 ± 0.20).
344 Effort significantly predicted Peak across keys (table 1 model 6). Birds that experienced Hard begging
345 effort as nestlings had earlier Peaks than those that had experienced Easy begging effort (estimated
346 marginal means \pm SE: Hard -0.26 ± 0.15 , Easy 0.29 ± 0.16). Effort also significantly predicted Peak
347 Rate (table 1 model 7). Birds that experienced Easy begging effort as nestlings had a higher Peak
348 Rate than those that had experienced Hard begging effort (estimated marginal means \pm SE: Hard
349 0.51 ± 0.06 , Easy 0.70 ± 0.06). There was also a significant effect of key: birds showed higher Peak
350 Rate on the lefthand key than the other two keys (table 1 model 6; estimated marginal means \pm SE:
351 Left key 0.72 ± 0.05 , Centre key 0.53 ± 0.05 , Right key 0.55 ± 0.05). We found no significant effect of
352 sex on any of the measures of timing performance (table 1 models 3-7).

353 There was evidence of individual consistency. When the data from the final four days of PROBE trials
354 were split into the penultimate two and last two days, individual identity accounted for 60% of the
355 variance in fixed imprecision and 71% in proportional imprecision. In contrast, the variance
356 accounted for by natal family was estimated at zero for both fixed and proportional imprecision.

357 **Discussion**

358 Our starting point was recent rat findings showing that greater timing imprecision is associated with
359 greater impulsivity (Marshall et al. 2014; McClure et al. 2014; Smith et al. 2015). We first sought,
360 through a numerical model, to establish why this should be the case. Our model highlighted the
361 importance of distinguishing between fixed imprecision (the constant amount of imprecision that
362 applies independently of the delay to be timed) and proportional imprecision (the amount by which
363 imprecision increases as the delay to be timed increases). The model predicted that greater
364 imprecision should increase impulsivity only for fixed imprecision; for proportional imprecision,
365 greater imprecision should in fact reduce impulsivity. We then measured timing imprecision in a
366 cohort of European starlings whose impulsivity had been previously measured. We found,

367 qualitatively supporting the predictions of the model, that greater fixed imprecision tended to
368 associate with greater impulsivity, whilst greater proportional imprecision was associated with less
369 impulsivity.

370
371 The reasons that the effects of the two types of imprecision are predicted by the model to be in
372 opposite directions are as follows. Increasing the fixed imprecision means adding a fixed amount of
373 noise to the perception of the duration of both delays. As this is the same amount of extra noise for
374 both, it has a proportionately greater over-valuing effect on the smaller-sooner reward, since the
375 discount function is steeper at shorter delays, and hence the impact of any given amount of over- or
376 under-perception is larger. On the other hand, increasing the proportional imprecision means
377 adding an amount of noise to the perception of the delay that is much larger for the longer duration.
378 This larger increment of extra noise overwhelms the fact that the discount function is flatter in the
379 vicinity of the long delay, and hence produces a greater over-valuing effect on the larger-later
380 reward relative to the smaller-sooner. In short, the marginal impact of increased imprecision on the
381 relative valuation of a smaller-sooner and a larger-later reward depends entirely on how that
382 imprecision is added: as a fixed constant regardless of delay, or as a scaling factor proportional to
383 the delay.

384
385 In our starling study, we separated out, for the first time, the fixed and proportional components of
386 timing imprecision. We were able to do this because the tri-peak temporal reproduction task
387 provides estimates of imprecision for the same individual for three different intervals, allowing us to
388 extract an intercept and a slope for the relationship of imprecision to the fixed interval, and hence
389 separately characterise fixed and proportional imprecision. An important conclusion from our data
390 is that starling timing does not show the scalar variance property. The fact that imprecision increases
391 for long intervals is often taken as an informal test of scalar variance (Lejeune and Wearden 2006;
392 Wearden and Lejeune 2008). Strict scalar variance is a stronger claim though: the ratio of the
393 imprecision to the FI must be constant across FIs, or, equivalently, a regression line of imprecision on
394 FI should pass through the origin. We found this was not so: in our starlings, the ratio of the
395 imprecision to the FI decreased with increasing FI, and the regression line of imprecision on FI had a
396 positive intercept. The conclusions from this starling study about how impulsivity relates to timing
397 imprecision depend very much on which of the two imprecision measures one uses: greater
398 imprecision tends to be associated with greater impulsivity if you use the fixed (intercept, α)
399 measure, but it is associated with less impulsivity if you use the proportional (slope, β) measure.
400 Thus, our starling findings conform to both the assumptions and the predictions of the numerical
401 model.

402
403 Are our starling findings consistent with those from the three rat studies (Marshall et al. 2014;
404 McClure et al. 2014; Smith et al. 2015)? They are in the same direction, albeit non-significantly in our
405 case, if we use our fixed timing imprecision measure, but they appear to be in the contrary direction
406 if we use our proportional timing imprecision measure. None of the three previous rat studies
407 separately reports timing imprecision at different durations, nor attempts to distinguish the fixed
408 and proportional components of imprecision. The clear guidance to the field, then, is to consider
409 carefully whether the measure of timing imprecision being used reflects predominantly fixed
410 imprecision, in which case we might predict a positive association with impulsivity; proportional
411 imprecision, in which case we might predict a negative association; or some mixture of the two, in
412 which case predictions are hard to make. We suggest that imprecision measures taken at very short
413 durations are likely to reflect mostly fixed imprecision, whereas those taken at longer durations are
414 likely to reflect mostly proportional imprecision. For example, in our starling data, the imprecision
415 measured by the Spread of the best-fitting polynomial at the longest FI (45 s) was near-perfectly

416 positively correlated with the proportional imprecision ($r = 0.99$); whereas the fixed imprecision was
417 significantly positively correlated with the Spread at 15 s ($r = 0.41$; though, curiously, not the Spread
418 at 5 s, $r = -0.01$). Thus, whether a single measure of imprecision mainly reflects fixed or proportional
419 imprecision depends how short or long a duration it is measured at. What constitutes a 'short' or a
420 'long' duration will depend on the discount rate of the species in question. The study by McClure et
421 al. (2014), for example, measured imprecision at 11 s, which is closer to our medium delay.
422 However, rats have lower discount rates than starlings (Bateson et al. 2015).

423

424 In addition to testing the predictions of our model concerning the relationship of timing precision to
425 impulsivity, our empirical study provided detailed data on individual variation in timing in the
426 starling. Birds learned the tri-peak procedure readily, and their responses conformed to the
427 expectations of the paradigm. That is, the peck rate on each key on the PROBE trials showed a single
428 peak close to the trained fixed interval, with a rapid rise before and a slightly slower decline after the
429 interval had passed. By separating each individual's data into two halves (the final two days and the
430 two days prior to this), we were able to show that individuals were somewhat consistent in both
431 their fixed and proportional imprecision, suggesting that these are stable individual differences. We
432 did not detect any natal-family effects. This result is somewhat surprising given the occurrence of
433 genetic polymorphisms implicated in temporal perception in humans and between-strain differences
434 in rats (Marinho et al. 2018), although we note our relatively small sample of starlings and especially
435 of natal families (8 families were represented). Our birds also all originated from a single population.

436

437 We did not find support for our prediction that the same developmental factors that we have shown
438 to affect impulsivity in these birds (namely, Hard begging effort and Lean amount) should also affect
439 timing imprecision. This would follow logically from the claim that a substantial driver of variation in
440 impulsivity is variation in timing imprecision. However, the developmental effects on fixed and
441 proportional imprecision were not significant. Our other exploratory results concerning
442 developmental experience relate to some of our previous findings with this cohort of birds. In the
443 present study we found that birds which were made to beg harder as nestlings (the Hard treatment)
444 had earlier Peaks, but lower Peak Rates. In previous studies, we have found these same Hard birds
445 to better defend their rate of energy intake when foraging is effortful (Neville et al. 2017; Dunn et al.
446 2018). On the other hand, they maintained lower body weights, presumably by eating less overall.
447 Here, it seems that their lower Peak Rate, which might suggest lower food motivation, patterns with
448 their lower bodyweights; whilst their earlier Peaks, which might suggest some exploration of the key
449 even before the FI has timed out, patterns with their defence of their rate of energy intake. We also
450 found that birds that experienced restricted early food supply (the Lean treatment) had poorer
451 precision as measured by the Spreads across the individual keys. This would suggest the importance
452 of early nutrition in the development of precise timing.

453

454 A key limitation of our study is that fixed and proportional imprecision were highly (negatively)
455 collinear. This prevented us entering both terms in the same model to predict impulsivity, which, if
456 possible, would have been preferable as a test of the numerical model. It is possible that this
457 negative dependence is a genuine biological relationship. However, we note that it could be at least
458 partly an artefact of measurement error. With imprecision estimated from just three FIs, there is a
459 substantial amount of measurement error on the slope of the regression of imprecision on FI (i.e.
460 the proportional imprecision). Any measurement error that causes this slope to be measured as
461 steeper than it really is, is also likely to lead to an estimate of the intercept as lower than it really is.
462 Any measurement error that causes the slope to be measured as flatter than it really is will tend to
463 lead to an estimated intercept that is larger than it should be. Thus, the strong negative dependence
464 of fixed and proportional imprecision, which almost guarantees that their respective effects on

465 impulsivity will be in contrary directions (as predicted by the numerical model), could in part be a
466 consequence of coupling due to shared measurement error. Future investigations should measure
467 fixed and proportional imprecision at a greater number of distinct FIs to mitigate this issue.
468

469

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474 **Conflicts of interest.** The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

475 **Ethics approval.** The starling study was approved by Newcastle University Animal Welfare Ethical
476 Review Board committee and was conducted under U.K. Home Office project licence (number
477 PPL70/8089).

478 **Availability of data and code.** All raw data and code are freely available via the Zenodo repository
479 at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3971671> (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3971670).

480 **Authors' contributions.** Conceived the study: Clare Andrews. Developed tasks, programmes and
481 protocol: Clare Andrews, Jonathon Dunn, Melissa Bateson, Daniel Nettle. Carried out laboratory
482 experiments: Clare Andrews (timing), Jonathon Dunn (impulsivity). Reared the birds: Clare Andrews,
483 Melissa Bateson, Daniel Nettle. Data analysis: Clare Andrews, Daniel Nettle. Numerical model: Daniel
484 Nettle. Wrote manuscript: Clare Andrews, Daniel Nettle. Edited manuscript for content: Clare
485 Andrews, Daniel Nettle, Melissa Bateson.

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558 Table 1. Output of mixed models. SS: smaller-sooner.

Model	Response variable	Fixed predictor variables	Random effects	B (SE)	t	P-value	n
<i>Choice impulsivity</i>							
1	Proportion SS choices	Fixed imprecision	Natal family	0.06 (0.03)	1.81	0.083	27
		Sex:M		0.05 (0.06)	0.78	0.443	
2	Proportion SS choices	Proportional imprecision	Natal family	-0.10 (0.03)	-3.62	0.001	
		Sex:M		0.05 (0.05)	1.03	0.313	
<i>Interval timing precision</i>							
3	Fixed imprecision	Amount:Lean	Natal family	-0.16 (0.39)	-0.40	0.692	28
		Effort:Hard		-0.41 (0.39)	-1.06	0.300	
		Sex:M		-0.72 (0.43)	-1.67	0.106	
4	Proportional imprecision	Amount:Lean	Natal family	0.65 (0.38)	1.72	0.101	28
		Effort:Hard		0.45 (0.38)	1.19	0.247	
		Sex:M		0.06 (0.42)	0.14	0.887	
<i>Exploratory models</i>							
5	Spread (standardised by key)	Amount:Lean	Natal family/Bird	0.55 (0.23)	2.33	0.030	84
		Effort:Hard		0.18 (0.24)	0.76	0.457	
		Sex:M		-0.45 (0.27)	-1.66	0.110	
6	Peak (standardised by key)	Amount:Lean	Natal family/Bird	0.05 (0.24)	0.21	0.832	84
		Effort:Hard		-0.55 (0.24)	-2.32	0.023	

		Sex:M					
7	PeakRate	Amount:Lean	Natal family/Bird	-0.04 (0.16)	-0.46	0.646	84
		Effort:Hard		-0.19 (0.05)	-2.22	0.035	
		Sex:M		-0.01 (0.09)	-0.01	0.927	
		Key:Centre		-0.19 (0.05)	-3.64	<0.001	
		Key:Right		-0.17 (0.05)	-3.64	<0.001	

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590 Figure 1. Two components of individual differences in timing imprecision. The imprecision in
 591 interval timing increases with the interval to be timed. The solid and dashed lines show this
 592 relationship for two hypothetical individuals. Here, one individual (dashed line) is more
 593 imprecise than another (solid line), in terms of a larger intercept of the line describing the
 594 magnitude of imprecision for a given interval duration (α , fixed imprecision), and also in
 595 terms of this line having a steeper slope (β , proportional imprecision).
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Figure 2. Model predictions for the association between timing imprecision and impulsivity. A. Predicted effect of changes in the fixed component of timing imprecision (α) and the proportional component of timing imprecision (β) on the relative valuation of a smaller-sooner (SS) reward after 3 s and a larger-later reward after 8 s. Valuations are relative to those of an individual with perfectly precise timing. A higher relative valuation would lead to greater impulsivity. The discount rate is set at $k = 0.54$, an empirically derived estimate for starlings. B. As A, but with a higher discount rate, $k = 1$. C. As A, but with a lower discount rate, $k = 0.1$.

638 Figure 3. A. Overall tri-peak temporal reproduction procedure performance averaged across
 639 all birds. B., C. Plots from two individual birds with differing interval timing performance.
 640 Fitted polynomial shown (solid line). The individual (BGPP) in panel B panel shows greater
 641 imprecision (Spread) as compared to the individual (BGYY) in panel C. Data show the mean
 642 number of responses on each key in 0.5 s time bins during PROBE trials during the final 4
 643 days of the task. Vertical dashed reference lines show the FI durations on which birds were
 644 trained. Data for the remaining 25 birds are shown in Supporting Information, figure S2.
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688 Figure 4. Spread of responses against fixed interval duration, by bird. Data are from the final
 689 4 days of the tri-peak temporal reproduction task. Lines represent linear fits. Individual
 690 starlings are identified by a 4-letter code.

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696 Figure 5. A. Relationship between fixed imprecision in timing and the proportion of choices
 697 for the smaller-sooner reward in the impulsivity task. B. Relationship between proportional
 698 imprecision in timing and the proportion of choices for the smaller-sooner reward in the
 699 impulsivity task. Lines represent linear fits, and shaded areas 95% confidence intervals.

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Figure 6. Effects of developmental treatments on timing imprecision. A. Fixed imprecision. B. Proportional imprecision. Developmental treatments are Effort: H is Hard, E is Easy; Amount: L is Lean, P is Plenty. Shown are means \pm one standard error.